

EFFECTS OF MAGNETIC PROPERTIES OF MATERIALS ON COMPUTER DEVICES

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ABSTRACT

In this work we gave a brief reviewed on magnetic materials lithium, molybdenum, with molybdenum incorporated into silicon, their magnetization and spin dependency. Computers, floppy disks and hard disk record on a thin magnetic coating that exhibits some magnetic properties. Computational results of molybdenum and molybdenum with silicene were performed and their effects on computer devices were found to be of immense contribution to computer development. DFT calculation was carried out to obtain the total and minimum energy of magnetic materials which help to justify the stable point of the materials. Molybdenum Materials with spin dependency shows lower minimum and stability point. Without spin shows lower bulk modulus and also lower lattice constant.

Keywords: *Magnetic, Computer, Material Molybdenum*

1. Introduction:

Permanent magnets, magnetic recording tapes and computer disk depends directly on the magnetic properties of materials, when you store information on a computer disk, you are actually setting up an array of microscopic permanent magnets on the disk (Sear and Zemansky, 2012). Three broad classes of magnetic materials exist; paramagnetism, Diamagnetism and Ferromagnetisms. The atoms that make up all matter contain moving electrons and these electrons form microscopic current loops that produce magnetic fields of their own. In many materials these current are randomly oriented and cause no net magnetic fields. But in some materials an external field (a field produce by current outside the material) can cause these loops to become oriented preferentially with the field, so their magnetic fields add to their external field. We then say that the material is magnetized. This is called Bohr- Magneton.

Paramagnetism is a form of magnetism whereby certain materials are attracted by externally applied magnetic field. Paramagnetic materials include most chemical elements and some compounds, they have relative permeability ≥ 1 (a positive magnetic susceptibility) and hence are attracted to magnetic fields. The magnetic moment induced by the applied field is linear in the strength and rather weak. It typically requires a sensitive analytical balance to detect the effect and modern measurements on paramagnetic materials are often conducted with a SQUID magnetometer (Nave, 2008). Paramagnetic materials have a small positive susceptibility to magnetic fields. These materials are slightly attracted by a magnetic field and the material

does not retain the magnetic properties when the filled is removed. Paramagnetic properties are due to the presence of some unpaired electrons and from the realignment of the electron paths caused by the external magnetic field. Paramagnetic materials include magnesium, molybdenum, lithium chromium and tantalum.

Application of high-temperature magnesium granular alloy are really important for nowadays, widely used for manufacturing of mobile phones, laptop computers, cameras and other electronic components. It is used for plastic packaging of electronic products such as mobile computers and communication devices (Ifrah, 2001). Molybdenum has a magnetization of $0.02\mu_g$ (Nelson, et al, 2010) as a result serve as computing devices that offer big improvement in processing speed. The material is made up of layers known as molybdenum oxides MO_2 which has unique properties that encourage the free flow of electrons at ultra-high speed. Computer, tablet and phones use lithium-ion battery. Because of its lightness and high energy density, lithium-ion batteries are ideal for portable devices such as notebook computers (Emery, 2002). Tantalum is mainly used today as tantalum capacitors in electronic equipment such as mobile phones, computers, DVD players and video games system.

Diamagnetism is the property of an object or material that causes it to create a magnetic field in opposition to an externally applied magnetic field. It is a quantum mechanical effect that occurs in all materials, where it is the only contribution to the magnetism the material is called a diamagnetic. It is not a permanent magnet. Its magnetic permeability is less than μ_0 that is $m_p < \mu_0$ (the permeability of free space). In most materials, diamagnetism is weak effect, but a superconductor repels the magnetic field entirely, apart from a thin layer at the surface.

It was first discovered when Sebald Justinus Brugmans observed in 1778 that bismuth and antimony were repelled by magnetic field, the solid state calculation of antimony was reported by Wang to be $-666mb$, while molecular calculation by Damovic *et al* (2006) yielded mutually consistent values of $-556mb$ and $-554mb$ both determination was based on current diatomic data of SbN, SbP, SbF and SbCl by Haiduke *et al* (2006). The term diamagnetism was coined by Faraday in September 1845, when he realized that every material responded (in either a diamagnetic or paramagnetic way) to an applied magnetic field. (ASM, 2000)

Ferromagnetism: the basic mechanism by which certain materials (such as iron Fe) form permanent magnets or are attracted to magnet is ferromagnetism like iron (Fe) with $14.41KeV$ $l = 3/2$, Mossbauer state Q is $160mb$ (Dufek, 1995), but with new value of $150(20)mb$ from nuclear theory (Martinez-Pinedo, et al., 2001) and by FLAPW calculation of Wdowik and Ruebenbauer giving $170(10)mb$ (Pekka, 2008) nickel (Ni), cobalt (Co) and many alloys containing these elements. Computer hard drive records data by magnetising ferromagnetic material. Sequential changes in the direction of magnetization represent patterns of binary data bits (Nave, 2008). The data is read from the disk by detecting the transitions in magnetization and decoding the originally written data. Different encoding schemes such as modified frequency modulation, group code recording, run-length limited encoding and others are used.

Hard disk drive (HDD) design consists of a spindle that holds flat circular disk called platters, onto which the data are recorded. The platters are made from a non-magnetic material,

usually aluminium alloy or glass and are coated with a shallow layer of magnetic material typically minimum in depth, with an outer layer of carbon for protection. The platters are spun at speeds varying from 3,000 RPM in energy-efficient portable devices, to 15,000 RPM for high performance servers. Information is written to and read from the patter as it rotates past devices called read-and-write heads (RWH) that operates very close over the magnetic surface. (Edward, 2001)

The RWH is used to detect and modify the magnetization of the material immediately under it. In modern drives there is one head for each magnetic platter surface on the spindle, mounted on a common arm. An access arm moves the heads on an arc across the patters as they spin, allowing each head to access almost the entire surface of the platter as it spins. The arm is moved using a voice coil actuator or in some older designs a stepper motor. For reliable storage of data, the recording material needs to resist self-demagnetization which occurs when the magnetic domain repels each other. Magnetic domains written too densely together to a weakly magnetize material will degrade over time due to physical rotation of one or more domains to cancel out these forces. The domains rotate sideways to a halfway position that weakens the readability of the domain and relieves the magnetic stresses. Older hard disk used iron (III) oxide as the magnetic material, but current disk use a cobalt based-alloy (Alkoy & Kelly, 2005) which magnetic sputtering has been reported earlier by Papdimitropoulos (2006) and Ogwu (2005) as well as its thermal excitation.

Computers, floppy disks and hard disk record on a thin magnetic coating. Credit, debit and ATM cards, all of these cards have a magnetic strip on one side. The strip encodes the information to contact an individual's financial institution and connects with their accounts.

Common television and computer monitors: TV and computer screens containing a cathode ray tube employ and electromagnet to guide electrons to the screen (wayne, 2002). It was reported that at high temperature some of the materials decoposes (Forrester, 1983)

Liquid crystal display (LCD) are used in a wide range of applications including calculators, printers, handsets and replaced cathode ray tube (CRT) displays in most application (Olsen, et al., 1982). In this work we reviewed magnetic properties and carried out simulation of few magnetic materials. The utility of this new class of magnetic is founded in the giant magnet or resistive (GMR) effect, identified in the last 1980s by layering conductors with domain-oriented layers of magnetic thin films, a large resistance change can be induced in the conductor. This can be understood from the interaction of electric and magnetic field in current transport on molybdenum and Cu_2O (Martha, 1996).

2. Methodology

Two methods were used to obtain the experimental and computational results. Standard test method was used for direct current magnetic properties of materials with D.C permeameters and ballistic test. Yoke were used to complete the magnetic circuit because they are inherently less accurate than ring test methods. However, when testing certain shapes as bars or when magnetic

field strength in excess of 200 Oe (15.9 or more KA/m) are required, when the test specimen is fabricated from a layer sample, it may not exhibit magnetic properties representative of the original sample. In such instances the test results, when viewed in context of past performance history will be useful for judging the suitability of the material for the intended application. All computational calculations presented in this work was done using the plane-wave expansion method as implemented in the ab-initio Quantum espresso-4.1(Pardew &Wang, 1992), based on density-functional theory, plane waves, and pseudo potentials (both norm-conserving and ultra-soft). The electron-ion interactions were described by ultra-soft pseudo potentials (Vandebilt, 1990), we employ Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE) for the exchange-correlation energy functional and a convergence criterion of 10^{-4} eV for the total electronic energy. The convergence threshold for the force and total energy was set to $1.0D - 5$ and $1.0D - 4$ respectively, the mixing beta was set to 0.6. Kinetic-energy cut-off was set to 35Ry the charge density cut-off was also set to 270Ry while the degauss was set to 0.01. Minimum and maximum energy varies.. We have also included spin dependence of the density and exchange correlation energy (results for two sets will be presented: one without spin and one with spin) in our analysis. In the calculation with spin, we consider only ferromagnetic ordering, as anti-ferromagnetic ordering is frustrated on a two-dimensional triangular lattice. Xmgrace was used to plot the graphs

3. Results and Discussion

The results are in two categories, first the experimental result and secondly the computational results of some magnetic materials

1. From the experimental work we observed that Computers, floppy disks and hard disk record on a thin magnetic coating and hence exhibit some magnetic properties. Credit, debit and ATM cards, all of these cards have a magnetic strip on one side which encodes the information to contact an individual's financial institution and connects with their accounts. Common television and computer monitors: TV and computer screens containing a cathode ray tube employ electromagnet to guide electrons to the screen. Liquid crystal display (LCD) are used in a wide range of applications including calculators, printers, handsets and replaced cathode ray tube (CRT) displays in most applications.
2. **Silicene with molybdenum:** Without Spin-Ecut 30 the k points 20 20 1 and lattice constant 7.88 bohr, the Minimum Energy of the completely relaxed structure was found to be $-48.316(Ry)$ with Lattice vectors See figure 1 The Bulk Modulus was calculated to be $80J/m^2$ using The Cohesive energy was obtained to be $-19eV$, while the stability energy was also calculated to $-9.36eV$. The Phonon Frequencies using (frozen phonon method) in cm^{-1} 4.4407 2.8389 0.0010 4.4409 2.8368 3.4478 0.0000 + 0.4307i 0.0018 0.0019 . The material without spin dependency at $E - cut$ 30Ry shows stability and cohesiveness with total minimum energy of $-48.316eV$

Figure1 Structures of Mo silicenes, an iso-surface of the electron density of MoSi₂ showing Si–Si bonds

3. **Silicene Molybdenum:** With Spin was calculated with $E - cut$ 30, k points 20 20 1 and Lattice constant 7.81 Bohr. The Minimum Energy of the completely relaxed structure was negative 48.317(Ry), which show more stable point than silicone incorporated into molybdenum The bulk energy was calculated to be $58.055 J/m^2$ with cohesive energy $-18.5eV$ and Stability energy $-9.065eV$ Phonon frequencies (using frozen phonon method) the eigen-values B were obtained as: 0.0160 0.0063 – 0.0000 0.0160 0.0087 0.0063 0.0006 – 0.0000 0.0000. The phonon frequencies (c was obtained using $3622.22 \times B^{0.5}$, where c phonon frequencies in cm^{-1} Conclusion from the above results shows that With spin there was an increase in the stability point compare to the material when there was nno spin see table 1, this result shows that there was signifying presence of magnetic spin. The cohesive energy of the material with spin was $-18.5eV$, which has a diiference of $-0.05eV$, this equally suggest the presence of spin or spin depedent material contribution. The bulk modulus shows a large difference, this shows that the presence of extra volume which was also accounted for as a result of the spin affected the materials

Material's status	Bulk modulus J/m^2	Lattice constant Bohr	Minimum energy eV	Minimum energy Ry	Stability energy eV	Cohesive energy eV
With spin	58.055	7.81 .	-657.40	-48.317	- 9.065	-18.5

and hence there as significant difference.

Table 1 showing the material properties of molybdenum with and without spin

Without-spin	80.00	7.88	-657.39	-48.316	-9.36	-19
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4. Conclusion

Magnetic properties of materials plays vital roles in understanding devices like light emitting diodes, field effect transistors and magnetic data. This film of magnetic materials can be used for high-speed disk memory devices or as permanent memory for computer applications. Devices such as these retain the state of the memory when power is turned off, in contrast to the volatile memory in a standard dynamic RAM device. Also such memory should consume a negligible amount of power when in operation, in contrast to the steady drain of semiconductor dynamic access memory (DRAM).

Magnetic materials can affect computer devices positively because most permanent or semi-permanent computer data is stored magnetically, meaning a stream of computer data (os and is) is stored by magnetizing tiny pieces of metal embedded on the surface of the disk or tape in a pattern that represents the data. Later, this magnetic pattern can be read and converted back into the same original stream of bits. This is the principle of magnetic storage. When using these materials careful should been adopted to address the contribution of the spin dependent materials like olybdenu, chromium, etc.

Our calculated phonon dispersion shows that silicene is stable absolute 0 Temperature in K. We show that silicene in its pure form exhibits a distortion of the honeycomb lattice see figure 2, when incorporated into molybdenum with spin the result is affected showing magnetic materials properties Our results should encourage experimental efforts to synthesize some of these systems, for the exploration of fundamental science as well as for applications both in computer and other electronic devices.

Figure 2 Structure of an iso-surface of the spin density of CrSi₂ showing that the magnetic moments are primarily at Cr sites.

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